

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE CREATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF CHATGPT IN ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10568709>

Abstract: The emergence of ChatGPT has attracted everyone's attention, so the use value and potential ethical challenges of AI technology have become the focus of hot discussion. This paper sorts out the value of ChatGPT applications in various industries and then puts forward some new problems about AI applications. Nowadays, people are worried that artificial intelligence will replace people's work, but no one denies that it is useful to apply artificial intelligence in different areas in the future. Therefore, this article will talk about the prospects for the future development of the application of new technologies similar to AI.

Keywords: AI technology, ChatGPT, technical ethics, new technology value.

ВАЖНОСТЬ СОЗДАНИЯ И РАЗВИТИЯ CHATGPT В ИСКУССТВЕННЫХ

Аннотация: Появление ChatGPT привлекло всеобщее внимание, поэтому потребительская ценность и потенциальные этические проблемы технологии искусственного интеллекта стали предметом горячих дискуссий. В этой статье выясняется ценность приложений ChatGPT в различных отраслях, а затем выдвигаются некоторые новые проблемы, связанные с приложениями ИИ. Сегодня люди обеспокоены тем, что искусственный интеллект заменит работу людей, но никто не отрицает, что в будущем полезно применять искусственный интеллект в разных сферах. Поэтому в этой статье пойдет речь о перспективах дальнейшего развития применения новых технологий, подобных ИИ.

Ключевые слова: технология искусственного интеллекта, ChatGPT, техническая этика, ценность новой технологии.

INTRODUCTION

It is amazing to see the rapid growth and popularity of OpenAI ChatGPT since its launch in December 2022. ChatGPT, a AI-based chat robot, offers a wide range of applications such as question and answer, text creation, language translation, classification, code creation. In just five days after its release, the platform has garnered nearly a million registered users, and in two months, that number has exceeded one million. The exponential growth of ChatGPT has made it the fastest growing AI app in history. Similarweb data shows that in January this year, ChatGPT employs an average of about 13 million visitors per day, which is twice as many as in December last year. In addition, the total number of users exceeded 100 million, setting a new record as the fastest internet app to reach this finish line. That win surpassed TikTok's previous record, which took nine months to overcome the 100 million user barrier. The widespread use of ChatGPT has shown its significant impact and value to users around the world.

MAIN PART

ChatGPT has the ability to communicate, which can answer subsequent questions in context during a conversation. However, the main reason it explodes around the world in such a short time is that ChatGPT can not only talk to users without problems, but also write poems and articles, and can also analyze codes in screenshots obtained by internet users. ChatGPT is a sibling model of InstructGPT that teaches you to follow instructions quickly and respond in detail.

Because ChatGPT uses reinforcing learning technology to learn from the opinions of human commentators that can be used for questions, reading comprehension, mental assault, and so on. A number of AI companies are engaged in the production of their own AI products to compete with ChatGPT. In other words, the emergence of ChatGPT has made the AI industry more prosperous. ChatGPT's pre-training language model technology has been used in many small industries. For example, data such as announcements and research reports are structured to increase data production efficiency; tracking and verifying large amounts of data to find valuable investment data; is offered high quality customer service by addressing customer questions more accurately and efficiently. ChatGPT is indeed widely used in a variety of fields and can significantly increase user efficiency. Even with the development of artificial intelligence technology in a short time, it is impossible to limit the updating of information, the accuracy of responses, the cost of calculation and other factors, and ChatGPT in some areas from "efficiency tools" to "production tools" can succeed until and thus completely replace some repetitive and basic human work. Some analysts have tried to create a quantitative trading model based on ChatGPT support, but the conclusion is that it is not realistic to develop mature and useful strategies based solely on the model provided by ChatGPT, because the model provided by ChatGPT is relatively simple, and the data cannot be analyzed and the parameter setting does not have logical support. In February 2023, according to Xinhua Finance, many well-known academic journals update editing rules for academic articles written by ChatGPT. Fan explicitly prohibits the registration of ChatGPT as a co-author, and the use of text produced by ChatGPT in articles is not permitted. This indicates that the text created by the large language model can also be used in an article containing ChatGPT, but it cannot be listed as a co-author of the article.

This reflects the dual features of AI technology. The reason ChatGPT has such power is that this is the first time AI has shown the public that its language skills are much higher than expected. Continuous communication, questioning unfounded questions, and skillful use of internet jargon have created an interactive experience of ChatGPT that is dependent on it. ChatGPT can even produce "very excellent" content, a ability that AI has never shown before. ChatGPT has reached a level of logical consistency and clear thinking for non-demanding content such as text advertising, news, and more. Many programmers asked ChatGPT to write basic code, and high school students and even college students were given homework with documents created by ChatGPT, which also worried the education system. ChatGPT has really caused a lot of new problems and ideas, but the tool itself is innocent.

There is a lot of controversy about ChatGPT products. On the one hand, it increases the operational efficiency of the project. For example, the use of artificial intelligence technology can significantly increase our writing efficiency, reduce some unnecessary language errors, and can also be used to analyze data that free our hands. Artificial intelligence, on the other hand, really causes a number of ethical issues, such as academic misconduct. Then, it is unknown at this time how artificial intelligence products will affect our daily lives and how the public will react to artificial intelligence-like products. Therefore, in this study, we first analyze the areas of application of ChatGPT from its value, then advise some people on ChatGPT in the form of field research, and analyze the survey results.

OpenAI has announced the launch of ChatGPT Plus, a pilot subscription plan for ChatGPT, which costs \$20 per month. Over the next few weeks, ChatGPT Plus will gain leadership in the United States and expand to other countries. OpenAI also said it will continue to improve and expand the ChatGPT Plus service based on user feedback and needs. In this process, ChatGPT

Plus is available at \$20 per month, and subscribers can serve more sustainably and faster than the free version, and testing new features and optimization is a priority. In addition, the company is actively exploring paid service plans, business plans and data package opportunities at lower prices. Other AIGC track players are also actively exploring. Take the AIGC single-horned Jasper, which focuses on “AI generation copywriting” as an example. It can automatically create Instagram names, record TikTok video scripts, ad marketing text, and other content.

According to Fortune, in 2022, OpenAI revenue was expected to be less than \$30 million, and its net loss was \$545 million. With the popularity of ChatGPT, it can further increase its losses, as every time users call it, it consumes more computing resources and bandwidth to OpenAI. Of course, OpenAI has also started trying to commercialize. In February 2023, OpenAI announced the launch of a \$20-priced ChatGPT Plus paid pilot subscription plan per month. The paid version has features such as duty-free, fast response at peak hours and prioritizing new features and improvements. According to OpenAI forecasts, as ChatGPT becomes an important tool for attracting customers, its revenue will grow rapidly, with an estimated revenue of \$ 200 million in 2023 and more than \$ 1 billion in 2024. It is also reported that Microsoft is in talks to invest about \$ 10 billion in OpenAI, which is also raising its value to \$ 29 billion. Previously, in 2019, Microsoft invested \$ 1 billion in OpenAI, providing it with significant financial support and Azure cloud computing.

In terms of business model and profitability, on the one hand, ChatGPT is not currently open source and its business model is not clear. At the same time, its performance process must continue to incur high costs, which will affect the rapid expansion of its ecosystem. There is no doubt that local AI technology companies will have the time and space to deal with it, but will create opportunities for other industry chain participants. On the other hand, the current technical level of ChatGPT has not reached the ideal state, it still takes some time to replicate the product and the environmental structure, as well as time to take advantage.

With the success of OpenAI, many companies have begun to follow these types of conversational AI products. Because the competitive pressure in the AI market is increasing. On February 7, 2023, BAIdu announced that the company’s “ChatGPT-like app” would complete internal testing in March and that the project name would be designated “ERNIE Bot”. As the first company to unveil a “ChatGPT-like” project in China, BAIdu also said Wenxin was sprinting before accessing the Internet. According to Google and Microsoft rhythms, Wenxin can pre-open the internal test. On February 8, 2023, Ali said that the Ali version of ChatGPT was being developed and is currently in the internal testing phase. NAILing also said that the Ali version of the ChatGPT dialog robot will be combined with nail depth. 360, JD.COM, said they had developed or planned to develop products related to Netease ChatGPT [2]. Iflytek said on the investor interaction platform that a technology similar to ChatGPT would take the lead in launching artificial intelligence research machine products in May this year.

The following service can be achieved using AI chat robot ChatGPT. In this case, the AI chat robot will help you answer general questions about watching and participating in ChatGPT, competition time, ticket information, assisting surrounding services and event organizers to respond immediately to the needs of fans, saving time and labor costs (Bag et al.), 2022). Second, use the ChatGPT artificial intelligence chat robot to enhance fan interaction: a trained ChatGPT can help the organizer update social media and release content in a sponsor-like tone. Third, the AI chat robot can output real-time game data by studying the AI event data set by applying ChatGPT to the sports news report. For example, German football media Ran automatically uses

the GPT3 language model to create news content, which significantly saves human costs and software production costs. Finally, ChatGPT can transcribe and translate oral or written content into other languages, which helps sports IPs become global.

It should be noted that many fitness bloggers and software engineers have recently started collecting and selling fitness plans created by ChatGPT, each ranging from \$15-30. Using ChatGPT to create a weight loss plan has certain advantages. As a well-trained AI robot, ChatGPT can respond quickly to user needs and create a complete plan in 20 minutes, including weight loss points, three-meal ratio, supermarket shopping list and sports plan.

Short-term changes in key sectors are mainly in three respects. First, there will be a combination of the two in the search engine area around ChatGPT in the short term. Second, in the field of smart customer service, if ChatGPT can implement customer service function, it will be an achievement in reducing human costs. Third, the NLP is in the field of application because it is essentially a sequential language model, downstream machine translation and other areas will also be developed to improve the chatgpt model capability and the upper limit of field technology [3].

With the rapid development of ChatGPT, ChatGPT is beginning to make great strides in the field of NLP as a key model of NLP, including data acquisition, machine translation, small sample transfer studies, and other research areas (Cetinic & She, 2022). High-flow data interpretation, computing power, data cleaning, data collection, and other areas are facing strong developments. Downstream, smart customer service, chat robots and other software industries are thriving. Currently, smart customer service in local e-commerce and other areas does not have the ability to communicate in many ways. By updating open dialogue models such as ChatGPT, smart customer service makes the leap to human costs [4].

In the search engine industry, ChatGPT cannot currently replace the search engine function. First of all, it is based on a comprehensive model, the ability to adopt new knowledge is not friendly, and the cost of training and experience to update the model is high. Second, if a large number of user requests are encountered by real search engines, the cost of online thinking is high. The combination of search engines and the ChatGPT model can become the mainstream of search engines. Some foreign manufacturers have gradually introduced similar ChatGPT features into search engines.

CONCLUSION

ChatGPT shows us the way to the future AI world. In recent times, most companies have become more popular with virtual people and AIGC concepts. There are still limitations to the use of ChatGPT, and efforts are still underway to optimize the model. The upper limit of the ChatGPT model is determined by its model, which requires a large workforce and a wide range of users to suit the real world. ChatGPT may face problems such as creating non-existent knowledge or subjectively guessing the questioner's opinion, and model optimization will continue unabated. If the iteration of AI technology is less than expected and the optimization of the NLP model is limited, it will affect the development of relevant industries. In addition, the model of ChatGPT is still in the research phase and the next commercialization process should be seen. ChatGPT can answer constant questions, admit mistakes, question misconceptions, and even reject unfounded claims. Communication and interaction between users and ChatGPT includes simple conversation, information advice, writing and writing poetry, and modifying program codes. Feedback provided by users during the use process is the most valuable information for OpenAI, which can constantly teach language models and correct incorrect answers.

In addition, ChatGPT may diversify program prospects in the future: First, chatbots need models like ChatGPT to provide dialogue capabilities, chatbots need to be fun and better accompany and serve people. However, this ability can also be incorporated into the robot's body, which makes the humanoid robot smarter and more human-like in the future. Second, many developers can use a basic platform like ChatGPT to optimize the model according to different industries and scenarios based on large models, so that, creating a variety of rich applications that meet the needs of users and thereby forming a conversational AI. The third is to be a professional human assistant in education, medical care, advertising and marketing, e-commerce, market and strategic consulting, enterprise services, coding, other areas, and other professional services, they can not only create content, but also call for different professional skills and even replace some basic professional work. Even if they don't attend the meeting, the smart browsing feature helps users create meeting minutes and key points. ChatGPT can also provide users with personalized timeline icons to quickly check sharing and discussion content. Fourth, the innovation combined with other modal AI tools, combining ChatGPT with images, text-generated videos, and even tools that will create direct 3D models in the future, UGC can bring huge benefits to content and become a key engine of content industrialization. In the future, chatgpt's integrated innovation with more information technologies, such as artificial intelligence and cloud computing, will create the tools to change the productivity line and become a new driving force for economic development.

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